

Driving European microelectronics excellence: SAL bridging research, industry, and innovation

Best practice category

Strengthening research & design capabilities; Partner collaboration and open ecosystems; Funding and policy

Stakeholder group

Research institutions

Value chain position

R&D, Chip Design, Fabrication

General Information

Silicon Austria Labs (SAL) represents Austria's top research hub for electronic and software-based systems, with key facilities located in **Graz**, **Linz**, and **Villach**. Officially founded in December 2018, SAL brings together over 350 researchers and technicians working across the entire ESBS value chain, from chip design and micro/nano fabrication to system integration, characterisation, and testing. SAL plays a central role in European microelectronics; It combines applied research, industrial collaboration and international partnerships to strengthen technological sovereignty, innovation and competitiveness. The main research areas are microsystems, sensor systems, intelligent wireless systems, power electronics, and embedded systems, offering technologies for Industry 4.0, but also the Internet of Things, autonomous driving, cyber-physical systems, AI, smart cities and energy, and smart health. It also operates on multiple levels: modeling, embedded hardware and software, integrating comprehensive knowledge of system integration. The center is structured as a GmbH (limited liability company) with a total public-private financing of approximately €228.5 million until 2026 and major shareholders such as the Republic of Austria, the provinces of Styria and Carinthia, Upper Austrian Research GmbH, and FEEI.

Activities and best practices

- The success of Silicon Austria Labs (SAL) hinges on the synergy between academic excellence and industrial needs. Through SAL-Uni Labs, the center combines university expertise with applied research, transforming high-level scientific discoveries into industry-ready solutions. Some Universities that collaborates with the centre are JKU Linz, TU Graz and University of Klagenfurt. In parallel, SAL invests in the talent of the future with the SAL Doctoral College, which acts as a specialised training hub where fellows work at the intersection of industry and academia, gaining experience in a highly international and intersectoral environment, and the CRYSTALLINE program: This is an European early-stage researchers (ESRs) training programme which aims to train future leaders in Electronic Based Systems (EBS) research, with a path of 60 months and with the aim of completing the PhD in 48 months. The offer is an interdisciplinary, international and intersectoral training, with research activities held in SAL laboratories, but also visits and secondment to partner universities, as well as collaborations with industry.

- Sal also has a **cooperative approach** and model which facilitates collaboration between industry and research, accelerating the implementation of innovative ideas. Thanks to this model, clients can quickly implement research projects with co-financing of **50% of costs**, without depending on the industrial sector and with flexibility based on the number of partners involved. This approach reduces bureaucracy, increases efficiency, and allows for a rapid shift from research to practical application. Furthermore, Through specific “project calls”, SAL invites startups, SMEs and large companies to participate in international project consortia to develop innovative solutions together.
- SAL also provides state-of-the-art infrastructure, including ISO class 5 cleanrooms and micro-nano prototyping services, which enable the transformation of scientific concepts into applied demonstrations and prototypes of M(O)EMS components, sensors, and integrated systems. This accelerates technology transfer to industry and helps bridge the gap between low TRL research and industrial solutions.

Challenges addressed with this practice

SAL's research and operational model addresses some of the key challenges of the semiconductor and embedded systems ecosystem, such as the gap between basic research and industrialisation and the technical complexity of advanced microsystems and sensors. SAL transforms scientific concepts into working prototypes, reducing technology transfer times to industry. At the same time, through international project calls and its cooperative model, the center fosters international collaborations between startups, SMEs, and large companies, combining specialised knowledge and innovative technologies. Finally, the training of highly qualified talent through programmes such as the SAL Doctoral College and CRYSTALINE helps to create a community of researchers capable of supporting complex challenges, thereby promoting technological autonomy and European resilience.